

METHODS OF WASTEWATER TREATMENT FROM EPOXY RESIN

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Abstract. The industry and the intensity of production determine the volume of wastewater use and types of pollution. In cities with developed industry, about 60% is allocated for enterprises, 25% for housing and communal needs, 9% for agriculture and 3% for everything else. Today, enterprises have a wide range of methods and equipment. In order to preserve the environment and comply with all established standards, it is necessary to regularly analyze wastewater and regulate the degree of purification. Modern methods of physico-chemical purification are based on minimizing the use of hazardous and non-degradable materials. The scientific and production enterprise offers equipment for cleaning industrial wastewater.

This article provides some methods focusing on the composition of epoxy resin effluents.

Keywords: wastewater, physico-chemical composition, pollution level, emulsions, soluble chlorides.

Аннотация. Отрасль и интенсивность производства определяют объемы использования сточных вод и виды загрязнений. В городах с развитой промышленностью около 60% отводится под предприятия, 25% – под жилищно-коммунальные нужды, 9% – на сельское хозяйство и 3% на всё остальное. Сегодня у предприятий есть большой выбор методов и оборудования. С целью сохранения экологии и соблюдения всех установленных норм необходимо регулярно проводить анализ стоков и регулировать степень очистки. Современные способы физико-химической очистки основываются на минимизации использования опасных и не подверженных разложению. Научно-производственное предприятие предлагает оборудование для очистки производственных стоков.

В этой статье приведены некоторые методы ориентируясь на состав стоков с эпоксидной смолы.

Ключевые слова: сточные воды, физико-химический состав, уровень загрязнения, эмульсии, растворимые хлориды.

Annotatsiya. Sanoat va ishlab chiqarish intensivligi oqava suvlardan foydalanish hajmini va ifloslanish turlarini aniqlaydi. Rivojlangan sanoat bilan shaharlarda, atrofida 60% korxonalar uchun ajratilgan, 25% uy-joy va kommunal ehtiyojlari uchun, 9% qishloq xo'jaligi uchun va 3% har bir narsa uchun. Bugungi kunda korxonalarda keng turdagi usul va uskunalari mavjud. Atrof-muhitni saqlash va barcha belgilangan standartlarga rioya qilish uchun oqava suvlarni muntazam ravishda tahlil qilish va tozalash darajasini tartibga solish kerak. Fizik-kimyoviy tozalashning zamonaviy usullari xavfli va parchalanmaydigan materiallardan foydalanishni minimallashtirishga asoslangan. Ilmiy-ishlab chiqarish korxonasi sanoat oqava suvlarini tozalash uchun uskunalari taklif etadi.

Ushbu maqolada epoksi qatroni oqava suvlarining tarkibiga e'tibor qaratadigan ba'zi usullar keltirilgan.

Kalitsozlar: chiqindi suv, fizik-kimyoviy tarkibi, ifloslanish darajasi, emulsiyalar, eriydigan xloridlar.

Introduction: Wastewater is discharged into reservoirs of industrial facilities and settlements through a sewer system or by gravity. Therefore, they can be divided into several types:

- production (formed due to technological processes): conditionally clean (do not change the physico-chemical composition of the reservoir and do not require special cleaning);
- normatively purified (the level of contamination does not exceed the threshold value of the norm);
- contaminated mainly with organic impurities;
- contaminated mainly with mineral impurities;
- contaminated with a mixture of organic and mineral impurities;
- household (formed due to human activity, as well as after using showers, baths, laundries, hospitals, canteens);
- atmospheric or stormwater (formed after precipitation)

Consider the distinctive characteristics in the form of flotation wastewater treatment from epoxy resin.

Research methods: It is possible to clean the wastewater of an epoxy resin manufacturing plant. At the same time, it is possible to achieve the following results:

Toluene. It is practically insoluble in water. Such large initial values indicated in the "Requirements for the composition of wastewater" are due to the fact that it is in the form of an emulsion in wastewater. As soon as we perform demulsification, the toluene concentration will decrease to the level of solubility in water, which is much closer to the MPC[1].

Sodium chloride. Of course, you can remove it. This allows us to make the hydrotation process that we have mastered. However, we immediately emphasize that if this indicator is really not critical, then it is better not to even take up this case. Since the implementation of this process will require large additional costs. Simply put, it will cost almost more than everything else combined. Therefore, we propose at the first stage to master the technology of water purification from colloids, and to return to purification from soluble sodium chloride later if necessary. The rest of these indicators (epichlorohydrin, tarry substances, crosslinked epoxy resin) will be considered as a single complex of substances. It is with this holistic approach that our proposal is connected[2]. To solve this problem, we offer you the following option: organize the cleaning process in 2 stages.

Stage 1. Used:

- components of the Reagentless Water Treatment System (SBPV) configured for the hydrocarbon treatment mode;
- heavy resinous oils, preferably with a high sulfur content. Consumption is about 50-100 kg. per hour. They are used to coagulate cross-linked epoxy resin and form strong tar-like complexes during electromagnetic treatment (without this treatment it is almost impossible to reduce the hazard class). At the first stage of purification, we propose to use the working scheme of the developed UPN (oil treatment plant), which includes the following SBP devices: Decarbon, KOED, KOEH, Jet mixer (for mixing water with oil), Sanar (in UPN this device is called a loop reactor), Sump tank, Pumps, Instrumentation. High pressures and temperatures have learned to

change the fractional and hydrocarbon composition of oil in the process of preparing it for processing, and to refine light petroleum products [3].

Results: The essence of the proposed technological process: oil is mixed with contaminated wastewater and treated with structured electromagnetic fields, as a result of which we will have four layers in the demulsification tank at the end of the first stage of purification:

1. Toluene associated with light petroleum fractions. Thus, toluene will be isolated from the water, where it was in the form of an emulsion.

2. The mother layer with heavy fractions of oil with epichlorohydrin and resinous substances.

3. Epichlorohydrin is a water-soluble intermediate obtained during the production of epoxy resin, chemically active. It binds very well to heavy oil fractions. Thus, epichlorohydrin and resinous substances will be isolated from the water.

4. Water containing soluble chlorides (sodium chloride) and a small amount of petroleum products. That is, we received purified water, from everything required, except sodium chloride. But a small amount of oil fractions (<1%) will enter the water.

Thus, after the first stage, there remains water (650-700 liters / hour, which must be refined in the second stage) and a tar-like mixture (300-350 kg / hour), the hazard class of which will correspond to fuel oil, tar, and non-distilled oil. This semi-finished product with a great technological effect can be sold to the nearest asphalt concrete plant [4]. High-grade polymer concrete road surface is made of it (for example, the landing decks of modern aircraft carriers are made of polymer concrete). If necessary (after dehydration), it can be packed in kraft bags and stored indefinitely. As a last resort, it can be burned in coal-fired furnaces with layered combustion.

Stage 2. At this stage, the purification of the resulting water is realized, namely, the separation of residual petroleum products contained in it in the form of an emulsion. In this case, only SBPV units (the second set) are used, configured for water treatment mode, without the use of reagents. The essence of the proposed technological process: water is treated with structured electromagnetic fields, as a result of which we will have two pronounced layers in the demulsification tank at the end of the second stage of purification:

- A small amount (<1%) of light petroleum fractions (gasoline class) that can be easily disposed of.

- Purified process water that meets the requirements (except for the requirements for sodium chloride).

Thus, the requirements for quantitative content will be met impurities. If the proposed cleaning option suits you, then we will proceed to detail the technical and commercial proposal. For example, we will need information about the volume of wastewater being processed, the pH of wastewater at the inlet, and the desired pH of water at the outlet (because in our technological process we change the pH of the medium).

Conclusion

1. These data determine the design of the devices included in the SBP, the complete equipment, as well as, accordingly, the total price of the project.

2. You will need information about the volume of wastewater being processed, the pH of wastewater at the inlet, and the desired pH of water at the outlet (because in our technological process we change the pH of the medium).

3. During long-term operation, the accumulation of this sediment is possible. As it accumulates, it will need to be periodically removed from the container and fed to the first stage.

4. Bottom sediment containing coagulant (crosslinked epoxy resin, asphaltenes of oil, etc.). Thus, all suspended substances will be transferred from water to bottom sediment.

REFERENCES

1. Saydullaev S. R. DECISION-MAKING SYSTEM FOR THE RATIONAL USE OF WATER RESOURCES //Journal of Central Asian Social Studies. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 01. - С. 56-65. <https://doi.org/10.37547/jcass/volume01issue01-a6>
2. Qutlimurodov, U. M. (2022). Prevention of water losses in zarafshan-gagarin main water system. In The Third International Scientific Conference Construction Mechanics, Hydraulics and Water Resources Engineering. (CONMECHYDRO 2021 AS). AIP Conference Proceedings **2612**, (Vol. 7, p. 23). 020034 (2023); <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0113247>.
3. Pirnazarov I.I. The soil of the seedlings in greenhouses heating by geothermal energy// An americ an scientific journal Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. Volume 4, January, 2022 , Part 20-24.
4. Ergashev, R., Ismoilov, N., Nasirova, N., Kholbutaev, B., Khusanbayeva, K., & Nazarov, O. (2021). Technology of water supply to water inlets of pumping stations. In IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering (Vol. 1030, No. 1, p. 012156). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1030/1/012156>
5. Ergashev, R., Azimov, A., Kholbutaev, B., & Mavlonov, L. (2021). Influence of cavitation on pressure pulsation through impeller of large pumps. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 264, p. 03004). EDP Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202126403004>
6. Pirnazarov I.I. The role of geothermal energy in the national economy//“GALAXY”// International interdisciplinary research journal (GIIRJ). An International Interdisciplinary Monthly Journal. Volume 10, Issue 1, January, 2022. Part , 114-117.
7. Кутлимуродов У.М. Решения для эффективного использования водных ресурсов в регионах Республики Узбекистан //Символ науки. – 2021. – №. 3
8. Tursunov, M. K., and B. B. Ulugbekov. "Optimization of the placement of solar collectors in a limited area." *Me'morchilik va qurilish muammolari* (2020).
9. Kutlimurodov, U.M. Atmospheric pollution with harmful substances and measures to reduce it. *Ecology: yesterday, today, tomorrow.*-2019. s, 249-252.
10. Meliev B. U., Saydullayev S. R. Penetrating waterproofing for concrete type “penetron”, its advantages and disadvantages//golden brain.-2023. т.1.№.1. с. 191-194.
11. Pirnazarov I.I., Boboyev S.M. Description of experimental devices in greenhouses and evaluation of errors of measurement control devices//Web of Agriculture: Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences//ISSN (E): 2938-3781.IFSIJ JIF: 7,335. Том.2 №3(2024):BAO.pp.21-29.
12. Karimovich, T. M., and S. A. Obidovich. "To increase the effectiveness of the use of Information Systems in the use of water." *Development issues of innovative economy in the agricultural sector* (2021): 222-225.
13. Кутлимуродов У.М. Некоторые аспекты экологических проблем, связанные с автомобильными транспортом //European Scientific Conference.
14. Masharipovich, Q.U. (2021). Laboratory Equipment of Overpressure Determination on Standard. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*,1(6), 138-143